

The Impact on Quality of Vision after Phacoemulsification with Implantation of Aspherical vs Spherical Monofocal Intraocular Foldable Lens – A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Aim: To compare the effect of aspheric Intra Ocular Lens (IOL) on post-operative quality of vision, which includes visual acuity, contrast sensitivity, and ocular aberration, versus conventional spherical IOLs after phacoemulsification cataract surgery.

Material and Methods: A single centre, hospital-based prospective observational comparative study was by enrolling a total of 181 patients who met the inclusion criteria. Participants were divided into two groups based on the type of IOLs. The data on the preoperative and postoperative outcome including assessment of visual acuity, on the 1st, 10th, and 30th days, and measured their IOP whereas intra ocular pressure, spherical aberrations, and contrast sensitivity at the 1-month postoperative day.

Results: There was no significant difference between the two study groups in terms of age, gender, or laterality of the eye. The mean age of the patients in this study was 62.77 ± 9.03 years, with no significant difference in gender distribution ($p = 0.368$) or laterality of eyes ($p = 0.997$) between the groups. At the 1-month post-operative visit, there was no statistically significant difference in uncorrected as well as corrected visual acuity, IOP between the two groups. However, there was a significant difference in the mean spherical equivalent ($p = 0.015$), suggesting that IOL designs influence spherical equivalent. Under photopic and mesopic luminance conditions, the contrast sensitivity of patients in the aspheric group was significantly better (P value < 0.05), but not significantly different under scotopic conditions. There were no significant difference in the mean Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) and Strehl Ratio (SR) at 3 mm in the optical zone between the two groups. The mean spherical aberration (SA) at 4 mm was 0.11 ± 0.09 , in group in comparison to group 2 0.04 ± 0.14 (p -value < 0.001). The remaining eye aberrometry measurements showed no statistically significant difference, i.e., lower order ($p = 0.275$), higher order ($p = 0.481$), and total ($p = 0.379$) aberrations between the two groups.

Conclusion: Aspheric IOLs, designed to correct positive corneal astigmatism, demonstrated superior contrast sensitivity at low spatial frequencies compared to spherical IOLs. However, no clinically relevant difference in best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) was observed between groups, suggesting no overall difference in final visual quality.

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Introduction

In India, cataract contributes significantly to preventable blindness, accounting for 50–80% of bilaterally blind individuals [1]. Cataract surgery is one of the most cost-effective interventions in the field of medicine, resulting in almost immediate visual rehabilitation. With ongoing improvements in biometry, surgical techniques, and intraocular lenses (IOL), cataract surgeons have been capable of achieving precise quantitative refractive results following cataract surgery. As a result of ongoing technological advancements, people now view cataract surgery as a refractive procedure, and cataract surgeons are now concentrating on

achieving good vision quality. Thus, to achieve the best possible quality of vision, the focus has shifted to other aspects of vision beyond Snellen visual acuity, such as contrast sensitivity and aberrations. [2]

After cataract surgery, implanting conventional spherical IOLs increases the positive spherical aberration in the eye, reducing visual performance. Aspheric IOLs are the newer IOLs that reflect the refractive shift in cataract surgery. [3] They eliminate the positive spherical aberration that conventional spherical IOLs add to the eye, resulting in increased optical performance.

Therefore, the goal of this study was to evaluate how the implantation of spherical and aspheric lenses affected the final refractive outcome, including contrast sensitivity.

Materials and Methods

We conducted this prospective observational comparative study on consecutive 181 patients, as calculated by Lemeshow et al. [4], who underwent cataract surgery, followed up to a one-month postoperative visit, and met the inclusion and exclusion criteria. In accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, we included the patients in the study after they gave their informed consent. This study included patients in good general health who were undergoing cataract surgery without any other ocular pathologies or complications during surgery. The exclusion criteria were those patients who underwent previous intra-ocular surgery, any history of ocular trauma, corneal degeneration, dystrophy or corneal scarring, glaucoma, optic nerve disease, macular and retinal disease, and patients with intra-operative complications (e.g., capsule rupture, vitreous loss, IOL not in bag). We divided the recruited patients, who met the inclusion criteria and gave written informed consent, into two groups based on their choice of intraocular lenses. We formed two groups based on the type of IOLs implanted during cataract extraction. Group 1 comprises 86 patients ($n = 86$) who received spherical IOLs without any attempt to correct their pre-existing positive corneal astigmatism, while Group 2 comprises 95 patients ($n = 95$) who received aspherical IOLs to correct their positive corneal astigmatism. A single experienced surgeon performed all the surgeries in this study using phacoemulsification under topical anesthesia and a corneoscleral 2.2 to 2.8-mm incision.

Data Collection

A single optometrist evaluated the visual acuity of all patients pre-operatively using the Snellen chart, conducting detailed examinations of the anterior and posterior segments. We also recorded demographic data such as age and gender. We assessed the following parameters during the 1-month follow-up visit: Uncorrected and correct distances We measured visual acuity (UDVA and CDVA) using the Snellen chart, tested contrast sensitivity using the F.A.C.T.-O PTEC® 6500 P (Stereo Optical Co., Inc., Chicago, IL) under mesopic (3.0 cd/m²) and photopic (85 cd/m²) luminance conditions, and performed aberrometry using iTrace (Tracey Technologies, Houston, TX). We measured all aberrations using a 3 mm pupil diameter, assuming this to be the average pupillary diameter in the Indian population. The iTrace operates based on the fundamental principle of ray-tracing aberrometry, employing an infrared light beam with a wavelength of 785 nm. iTrace's linear detectors enhance the precision of measuring each point's center, surpassing that of other aberrometry techniques. Additionally, it utilizes corneal topography data to e

xtract corneal and internal aberrations from total aberrations. The 3 mm optic zone also allowed for the determination of the modulation transfer function and nd point spread function (strehl ratio).

The IOLs used in this study were ADAPT-AO IOL from Bausch and Lomb, which is hydrophilic, and A S-6 from Acriol-EC, which is hydrophobic (Aurovue, Aurolab®). The study also used Acrysof IQ from Alcon® and HOYA 251, which are both hydrophobic aspheric IOLs. However, the patients made the final decision about IOL implantation after receiving proper counseling based on their needs and a thorough ophthalmic examination that included their astigmatism, aberrations, and job profile.

We entered the data in Microsoft Excel and analyzed them using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20.0. We expressed variables such as age, UCVA, BSCVA, CSF, and spherical aberration in terms of mean and standard deviation. We used non-parametric tests to establish an association between the two qualitative data, given the uneven distribution of the data. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

This study enrolled a total of 181 patients (181 eyes) and divided them into two groups. Group 1 had 86 patients as IOLs that did not attempt to correct the pre-existing positive corneal astigmatism, and Group 2 had 95 patients as IOLs that corrected the positive corneal astigmatism. The mean age of patients in the study population was 62.77 ± 9.03 years (range: 26–83 years). The mean age of patients opting for a spherical IOL was 63.51 ± 9.44 , while that of patients opting for an aspheric IOL was 62.09 ± 8.65 . There was no significant difference in mean age between the two groups ($p = 0.264$). Table 1 provides the patient's demographic details. Therefore, age did not affect the choice of IOL in this study. This study included 101 males and 80 females. The gender distribution between the two groups was not significant ($p = 0.368$), so gender played no role in choosing IOL in the two groups. Also in this study, 101 (56%) were right eyes and 80 (44%) were left eyes). There was no significant difference in eye distribution between the two groups ($p = 0.997$). In the study population, the mean pre-operative CDVA was 0.77 ± 0.63 log MAR. The mean preoperative CDVA was $0.87 (\pm 0.69)$ for the spherical IOL group, while it was $0.68 (\pm 0.56)$ in the aspherical IOL group, and there was no statistically significant difference in mean CDVA between the two groups ($p = 0.028$). This suggests that the IOL design does not influence preoperative CDVA.

At the one-month post-operative visit, the mean LogMAR UDVA for group 1 was $0.19 (\pm 0.13)$ and group 2 was $0.18 (\pm 0.14)$, and the mean LogMAR CDVA for group 1 was $0.04 (\pm 0.09)$ and for group

2 was $0.04 (\pm 0.08)$. There was no statistically significant difference in UDVA or CDVA between the two groups at the 1-month post-operative visit. It indicates that the IOL designs do not affect visual acuity. The mean spherical equivalent was -0.28 ± 0.44 in Group 1 and -0.13 ± 0.41 in Group 2. This difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.015$), which shows that IOL designs, like those found in spherical IOL, can change the spherical equivalent.

The postoperative contrast sensitivity testing after 1 month revealed significant differences between the groups under photopic and mesopic conditions. We performed F.A.C.T. contrast sensitivity testing without glare at 1 month post-operatively for photopic and mesopic luminance conditions. Area under curve under photopic conditions in group 1 was $21.37 (\pm 2.72)$ and in group 2 was $22.83 (\pm 3.48)$, which showed a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.032$) and was better in group 2. However, in group 1, the area under curve under scotopic conditions was 21.23 ± 2.79 , and in group 2, it was 22.24 ± 3.40 , which was statistically non-significant between the two groups ($p = 0.248$). Also, group 2 showed better photopic contrast sensitivity at various spatial frequencies in cycles per degree (cpd), i.e., 1.5, 3, 6, 12, and 18 cpd. At 1.5 cpd, the mean contrast sensitivity score for group 1 was 1.42 ± 0.13 and for group 2 it was 1.45 ± 0.16 . At 3 cpd, it was 1.71 ± 0.15 for group 1 and 1.75 ± 0.16 for group 2. At 6 cpd, it was 1.66 ± 0.16 for group 1 and 1.72 ± 0.16 for group 2. At 12 cpd, it was 1.24 ± 0.14 for group 1 and 1.32 ± 0.22 for group 2. At 18 cpd, it was 0.49 ± 0.35 for group 1 and 0.69 ± 0.39 for group 2. Similarly, we measured the area under mesopic luminance at various spatial frequencies in cycles per degree (cpd), specifically at 1.5, 3, 6, 12, and 18 cpd, and found that group 2 performed better. The mean contrast is measured using iTrace (Tracey Technologies, Houston, TX), a ray tracing technology that measures internal and corneal aberrations separately. The mean spherical aberration in group 1 was 0.02 ± 0.03 and in group 2 was 0.03 ± 0.03 , at a 3 mm optical zone, and the difference was not statistically different ($p = 0.075$). The mean corneal aberration in group 1 was 0.02 ± 0.02 and in group 2 was 0.02 ± 0.01 at the 3 mm optic zone, and the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.439$). However, the mean spherical aberration in group 1 was 0.11 ± 0.09 , which was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) than in group 2, where the mean SA was 0.04 ± 0.14 . This is to be expected, since eyes in group 2 had aspheric IOLs implanted to cancel out the effect of the positive corneal spherical aberration.

The remaining eye aberrometric values showed no statistically significant difference, i.e., in lower order ($p = 0.275$), higher order ($p = 0.481$), and total ($p = 0.379$) aberrations between the two groups. The sensitivity score (log base 10) under mesopic

conditions at a spatial frequency of 1.5 cpd in group 1 was 1.42 ± 0.14 and group 2 was 1.47 ± 0.17 ; at 3 cpd in group 1 was 1.71 ± 0.15 and group 2 was 1.76 ± 0.16 ; at 6 cpd in group 1 was 1.67 ± 0.16 and group 2 was 1.70 ± 0.18 ; at 12 cpd in group 1 was 1.22 ± 0.14 and group 2 was 1.29 ± 0.20 ; and at 18 cpd in group 1 was 0.47 ± 0.36 and group 2 was 0.58 ± 0.44 .

Also, the mean internal modulation transfer function (MTF) showed area under curve (AUC) at 3 mm optical zone in group 1 was 13.79 ± 3.41 , and in group 2 it was 13.23 ± 3.60 . The difference was not significant ($p = 0.90$). The average corneal modulation transfer function across various spatial frequencies revealed: In group 1, the area under curve at the 3 mm optical zone was 13.45 ± 4.56 , and in group 2, it was 13.64 ± 4.37 at the 3 mm optical zone ($p = 0.910$). and the mean total modulation transfer function at different spatial frequencies showed area under curve at 3 mm optical zone in group 1 was 10.95 ± 3.06 , and in group 2 was 10.45 ± 3.65 at 3 mm optical zone. The total mean Strehl ratio in group 1 was found to be 0.13 ± 0.08 , and in group 2, it was 0.14 ± 0.13 , and the difference was not significant between the two groups ($p = 0.409$).

Discussion

In this new era, there have been many advances and improvements in biometry, IOL technology and surgical techniques which improves the quality of vision after cataract surgery along with simple visual rehabilitation. Thus, modern cataract surgery not only aims at simple visual rehabilitation but also to achieve good quality of vision.

The quality of vision includes visual acuity, contrast sensitivity and ocular aberrations. Implantation of conventional monofocal spherical IOLs lead to increase in post-operative spherical aberration by introducing positive spherical aberration which is approximately $0.08 \mu\text{m}$ (over a 4 mm pupil) to pre-existing aberrations caused by the cornea [5,6].

Aspheric IOLs are the new technology IOLs which were designed to eliminate the residual spherical aberration post cataract extraction, aiding in improving the quality of vision especially under mesopic conditions with a physiologically dilated pupil. Hence, the quality of vision can be assessed in terms of visual acuity, contrast sensitivity and aberrations following the IOL implantation in post-operative phacoemulsification cataract surgery. [7]

This present study aimed to find the effect of aspheric IOLs on overall quality of vision, which includes all the above three parameters, and its advantages versus conventional spherical IOLs in post-operative patients who have undergone phacoemulsification cataract surgery.

The characteristics of various IOLs used in the study with zero and negative asphericity are described in the table below (table 1).

Table 1: Shows properties of various IOLs used in the study

	ADAPT- AO	AS – 6	ACRYSOFF- IQ	HOYA 251
Manufacturer	Bausch and Lomb	Acriol – EC	Alcon	Hoya surgical optics
Material	Hydrophilic acrylic	Hydrophobic acrylic	Hydrophobic acrylic	Hydrophobic acrylic
Optic size (mm)	6	6	6	6
Overall Length(mm)	10.5 – 11	12.5	13	12.5
Asphericity	0	0	-0.17	-0.18

The two study groups were comparable in terms of age, gender, laterality and pre-operative UCDVA and CDVA. Our study demonstrated no significant difference between the two groups in terms of uncorrected (0.371) and corrected distance visual acuity ($p=0.732$) at one month follow up visit including near visual acuity which is in contrast to study of Rocha et al⁷ and Holladay et al [8] concluded poor distance-corrected near acuity in

eyes with an aspheric IOL due to loss in depth of focus due to asphericity of lens.

The post-operative CDVA was similar in both spherical and aspherical IOL groups, along with intra-ocular pressure after 1 month follow-up which is similar to many studies. However, the mean spherical equivalent was significantly low in aspherical IOLs ($p=0.015$) as compared to spherical IOLs, showing the one of the property of aspherical IOLs.

Table 2: Visual acuity, Mean spherical equivalent and intraocular pressure at 1 month post-operative period

	TOTAL	GROUP 1	GROUP 2	p value
Mean UDVA	0.18 ± 0.13	0.19 ± 0.13	0.18 ± 0.14	0.371
Mean CDVA	0.04 ± 0.08	0.04 ± 0.09	0.04 ± 0.08	0.732
Mean Spherical equivalent (D)	-0.21 ± 0.43	-0.28 ± 0.44	-0.13 ± 0.41	0.015
Mean IOP (mm of Hg)	13.5 ± 2.81	13.40 ± 2.53	13.6 ± 3.05	0.523

The contrast sensitivity was performed in this study using F.A.C.T which is without glare, at photopic (85 cd/m^2) and mesopic (3 cd/m^2) conditions. The postoperative mean contrast sensitivity score (log base 10) revealed significant difference between two groups, indicating better performance of aspheric IOLs in both mesopic and photopic contrast sensitivity. The area under curve under photopic conditions in group 1 was 21.37 ± 2.72 and in group 2 was 22.83 ± 3.48 , which showed a statistically significant difference ($p=0.032$). However under scotopic condition, there was no significant difference ($p=0.248$) between two groups with the area under curve under scotopic conditions in group 1 was 21.23 ± 2.79 and in group 2 was 22.24 ± 3.40 . Kyung-Min Lee et al [9] conducted a study to compare quality of vision between three different IOLs- Tecnis Z9003, Acrysof IQ and Akreos Adapt AO. There was no significant difference in contrast sensitivity at 2 months but at 6 months.

The differences in contrast sensitivity were most pronounced with statistical significance under mesopic conditions at all spatial frequencies: 3, 6, 12, and 18 cpd as well as under photopic conditions in three spatial frequencies achieved statistically significance: 3, 6 and 18 cpd. Our study demonstrated a significant benefit in contrast sensitivity after the use of aspheric IOL compared with the spherical group. The reduced spherical aberrations could be the cause of the improved CS

in aspheric group, which corresponds with the results of some other studies. There was no statistically significant difference in mean pupil diameter under photopic, mesopic, and scotopic conditions across study groups. Also we measured the mean internal modulation transfer function, mean Corneal Modulation Transfer Function, mean total modulation transfer function at different spatial frequencies and the total mean Strehl ratio (Point spread function) at 3 mm optical zone which was statistically insignificant. It may be probably because the measurements were done for the 3 mm pupil where the benefit of the aspheric IOL would be at larger pupil size.

The spherical aberration was measured using aberrometry by iTrace (Tracey Technologies, Houston, Tx) which also provides facility to measure corneal and internal aberrations separately along with total aberrations, MTF and SR. [10,11] The mean spherical aberration in group 1 was 0.11 ± 0.09 , which was significantly higher ($p<0.001$), compared to group 2 in which Mean SA was 0.04 ± 0.14 as is to be expected since group 2 consisted of eyes in which aspheric IOLs were implanted to negate the effect of the positive corneal spherical aberration. In our study, group 2 showed significantly low Mean spherical aberration ($p<0.001$), compared to group 1. There was no statistically significant difference in Lower order ($p=0.275$), Higher order ($p=0.481$) and Total

($p=0.379$) aberrations, Trefoil and Coma between the two groups. Patrick F. et al [12], in their study found significantly less higher order aberrations and spherical aberration at 5 and 6 mm pupil diameters in Tecnis group (aspheric) compared to Clariflex (spheric) group at 3 months follow up visit using Hartmann-Shack aberrometer. The mean internal 3rd aberration and mean corneal 3rd aberration which includes vertical trefoil, vertical coma, horizontal coma and oblique trefoil and spherical aberration showed no statistical difference between two groups at 3mm optical zone. Kyung-Min Lee et al⁹, in their study found no significant difference at 2-month follow up in terms of HOAs and Zernike 3rd and 4th order aberrations among Tecnis, Acrysof IQ and Adapt AO groups. The difference in our study could be attributed to the comparison of aberrations done at 1month post-operative period only and at 3 mm optic zone using a ray tracing aberrometer.

Conclusion

Our study demonstrated that implantation of aspheric monofocal IOLs provides slightly better visual acuity than spherical monofocal IOLs. Aspherical IOLs also have better contrast sensitivity under photopic and mesopic conditions compared to spherical IOLs. This is because aspheric IOLs have much lower levels of internal spherical aberrations after surgery compared to spherical IOLs. This means that contrast sensitivity is better after surgery. Aspheric IOLs have negative spherical aberration to neutralize the positive corneal spherical aberration and hence restore the spherical aberration balance between the lens and the cornea. However, as spherical aberrations decrease, the depth of field may also decrease. However, the final visual quality was not different among the two groups. Hence, there was no clinically relevant difference in BCVA between aspheric and spherical IOL implantation. Given the higher cost of aspheric IOLs compared to spherical IOLs, we advise patients to consider the cost-benefit ratio and their visually demanding lifestyles based on their age and job profiles. This is especially important for individuals such as airplane pilots, nighttime drivers, and those who need to read in low light. For logistical reasons, we limited our study by not randomizing the group allocation. However, this is unlikely to have caused any selection bias, as the differences in the demographic and ocular baseline characteristics of the two groups were not statistically significant. The objective measures of visual quality, such as MTF and SR, were considered for the 3 mm pupil but did not show statistical significance. Measurements for a 5 or 6 mm pupil may have been statistically significant, as the benefits of the negative aspheric design could have been measurable at the larger pupil size. Further studies are necessary to understand the possibility of MTF and SR at various pupil sizes and

to conclude that the benefit of asphericity is significant.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors have no proprietary, funding, or conflicts of interest to disclose.

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